

USER SUPPORT SOLUTION IMPLEMENTATION FOR SAP ERP UTILIZING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO DRIVE AUTOMATED

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ABSTRACT

Hundreds of millions of help desk requests are received each year by major corporations with complex IT systems, such as SAP ERP. You can submit these requests using Service Desk or Service Manager (SM) online or by calling in. A type of software for managing corporate processes, "enterprise resource planning" integrates several programs to automate HR, IT, and service operations. An intelligent method to assist SAP ERP users is suggested in this research study. Automated replies to customer support inquiries are now a reality, which not only improves responsiveness to end users but also speeds up the investigation and resolution of problems. In order to efficiently interpret questions, the system employs machine learning techniques to categorize text into multiple classes. In order to provide the optimal reaction, the system employs a customized framework to retrieve evidence. The framework's conversational AI features make it possible to build chatbots that facilitate simultaneous group collaboration.

Keywords: SAP, ERP, Service Manager, Information Technology (IT).

Cite this Article: Vedaprada Raghunath. User support solution implementation for SAP ERP utilizing Artificial Intelligence to drive automated. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research and Development (IJAIRD)*, 2(1), 2024, pp. 123-134. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11261878>

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJAIRD/VOLUME_2_ISSUE_1/IJAIRD_02_01_012.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

In the course of the last several decades, technological developments have resulted in the creation of powerful computers that are not only more compact but also more affordable than they have ever been before. Because of this, firms now have easier access to more sophisticated mathematical tools. What are known as "intelligent technologies" are the tools that provide businesses the ability to delve deeply into the data pools that they currently possess in order to acquire analysis and business insight. If businesses make use of algorithms and automation, they will be able to implement digital and automated alternatives to the manual business processes that they are currently utilizing. An organization is said to be undergoing "digital transformation" when it moves away from using manual procedures and toward using digital ones. When it comes to adopting "smart" and intelligent technologies into its product line and features, SAP has been at the forefront of the industry throughout its history as one of the most prominent producers of software. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) that are integrated into corporate systems will assist customers in automating repetitive tasks and discovering new digital technologies. Data is used rather than explicitly programming rules in various applications. Within SAP applications, the cloud, and business networks, artificial intelligence is organically interwoven, which makes digital information easily consumable across the whole enterprise. Among other things, this may improve customer service, operations of the company, and the level of job satisfaction experienced by employees. This piece of software provides a cloud-based machine learning platform that is completely suitable for enterprise use. It interfaces without any problems with SAP's corporate software and machine learning capabilities, and it is easy to follow and utilize. When it comes to adding intelligence to company operations and applications, software engineers may make use of a platform that is both scalable and safe.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Computer science with the goal of simulating intelligence and behavior in humans or other animals was described as artificial intelligence. [1-3] An alternative definition of ML is the capacity of IT systems to autonomously discover answers to issues by identifying patterns in databases (Kersten et al., 2019).

AI has already made its way into several parts of the supply chain, and it might have a significant influence on both the beginning and the end of the process.[4-6] Artificial intelligence (AI) involvement unquestionably affects people's lives and society at large (Dwivedi et al., 2019). As an example, a US-based restaurant called KiwiBot used artificial intelligence to create tiny robotic vehicles that blend into cityscapes to carry food.[7-9] These vehicles are designed using a behavioral neural network. In addition to being more affordable and quicker, the business asserts that kiwiBots may make cities more pleasant places to live by easing traffic and other problems (Kiwibot, 2020). The appendix describes other examples of such general applications of AI and ML. [10-13] Nonetheless, the application of AI and ML in conjunction with SCM was the primary emphasis of this study.

The use of AI and ML is something that many companies are keen to do. [14-16] On the other hand, different countries take different approaches to implementing AI. For instance, with government backing, IT companies in the US are engaging in fierce competition to develop and apply AI and ML approaches. [17-19] In other countries, like China, the government oversees and controls all AI-related technologies (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2019). Ensuring citizens' privacy is effectively protected, EU countries have put limits on how data shall be acquired and utilized (Farrow, 2019).

Figure 1. Word cloud made from the keywords used

An argument put out by proponents of AI and ML is that, while these technologies may lead to the loss of certain employment, they will also usher in a period of unprecedented economic growth and job creation (Vocke et al., 2019). Everyone agrees that choices made on AI applications will affect various parts of people's lives. Hence, prior to making such life-altering decisions, comprehensive analyses and investigations are required (Dwivedi et al., 2019). All the benefits and drawbacks should be considered by industries as well. Take, for instance, the call for a systematic evaluation and the necessity of studying the effects of AI on industrial systems (namely, Industry 4.0) made by Lee et al. (2018) and Sundarakani et al. (2020). As Figure 1 shows, progress in AI and ML is happening at a rapid pace. [20-24] The purpose of this research is to examine the domain of highly cited publications in an effort to provide light on the extent to which organizations have used AI and ML and which models have been successfully tested. Further, new study has uncovered articles that have validated the untapped potential of AI and ML, which could pique the curiosity of other scholars (Toorajipour et al., 2021; Feizabadi, 2020). Thus, our research stands out because it provides a comprehensive overview of the AI and ML consequences for SC in its whole.

3. KEY TECHNOLOGY FOR THE INTELLIGENT ENTERPRISE

According to analysts, the worldwide market for AI in software experienced a growth of 20%-22% between 2021 and 2022. Between 2021 and 2025, this software industry is expected to experience a revenue growth of 39%, according to Forrester. The rise of AI is undeniably a megatrend. SAP has been eyeing this opportunity for a while now, and they plan to dominate the market for enterprise AI solutions for critical technology. The firm put money into its AI division, headed by seasoned researcher and AI specialist Dr. Feiyu Xu. In this case, the company's dominant market position, familiarity with business procedures across all industries, and access to the data needed to train the AI might all work as multipliers. Embedded AI is SAP's main focus. These are services that are integrated into industry solutions and quietly assist users. SAP also provides AI Business Services, which are individual microservices, and SAP AI Core and SAP AI Launchpad, which are infrastructure and tools, so that customers, partners, and business units of SAP may build their own AI projects.

Product management specialist Jana Wuerth said that "customers expect the solutions they buy from us to be intelligent by design" when discussing the artificial intelligence section. "At its finest, end users are oblivious to the fact that the solution is AI-powered; all they know is that it simplifies and improves their work." A wide variety of industries have contributed to the development of several hundred application cases. Notable clients include HPE, Dulux, Mitsui, and Döhler, in addition to numerous midmarket businesses. Experts training and testing these

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services with real customer data is the surest way to get the greatest results, as customers know. Because of this, a growing number of clients are releasing their system data to developers, subject to stringent data privacy requirements. "We are pleased that a lot of our customers are sharing their data with us, because it allows us to enhance the efficiency of their applications," remarks Dr. Xu, SAP's SVP and head of artificial intelligence worldwide.

AI Created on an Assembly Line

The success of this endeavor depends on the tight cooperation between the teams responsible for AI technology and the many lines of business. Applying AI in a factory-like fashion is what the SAP partnership model "AI Factory" is all about. This strategy allows SAP to deploy targeted solutions, including AI and other services that are ready to go, all in one place, for clients to use in a straightforward, efficient, and consistent manner. Several use cases for order automation are now being worked on by the team in collaboration with its line of business colleagues. To illustrate the point, in the past, clients who did not yet automate their orders but received them in PDF format had to manually enter the data into their system. Automated PO creation is now possible with the help of an AI solution that can extract data from PDFs. An upcoming feature will allow users to automatically fill in missing data by retrieving it from their order history. For instance, this may include the order type, plant, or route. Employees no longer need to go to the trouble of contacting their designated contact person to find out missing information. The precision of these services can reach as high as 90%, contingent upon the reliability of the input data. The quantity of orders requiring human intervention for processing or evaluation is thus minimal. As customers know from online purchasing, tailored recommendations are made possible by another AI technology from SAP. They are also utilized by SAP for its internal course offerings in the SAP SuccessFactors solutions HR development software. This allows workers to receive training offers that are relevant to their company roles and the courses they have already finished.

A robust, user-friendly, no-code development environment is integrated with SAP Intelligent Robotic Process Automation and the SAP Workflow Management service to form Intelligence in SAP Process Automation. People without coding skills may now create, modify, and enhance their own business applications and procedures. Furthermore, corporate processes are augmented by embedded AI, which enhances their intelligence and productivity. Returnable packaging management software from SAP is one option for a circular economy. It has been challenging for the various participants in the supply chain to coordinate on returnable packaging, including shipping pallets, due to heterogeneous data systems. Now, the various back-end systems may be better integrated with the aid of the AI solution, which is based on SAP Business Technology Platform.

Myriad Possibilities

The healthcare division is looking into an AI service that can handle hospital billing at the moment. It is crucial for healthcare providers to issue right invoices initially because, as backdrop, the German legislation made it more difficult to subsequently modify bills at the beginning of 2022. The system will suggest line items, including particular medications and services, that are commonly associated with a given treatment type when a person in the billing department types in "appendectomy," for instance. Not only can this make billing easier and faster, but it can also stop incomplete or incorrect bills from being created. We can only begin to scratch the surface of the potential future applications of artificial intelligence. For instance, by analyzing historical data for patterns that led to bottlenecks, AI integrated into an industry solution could anticipate disruptions in the supply chain. The procurement system has been trained to detect such hazards in the supply chain early on and search for alternatives, so companies might use AI to avoid purchasing products made with child labor in the future.

4. ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANNING BLOGS BY SAP

The value of AI at SAP

Terry: Artificial intelligence (AI) is the topic of today's discussion. Jurgen, could you tell me the value of AI and why SAP is investing in it?

Jürgen: Artificial intelligence (AI) isn't simply a buzzword; it's a real technology with several potential applications, especially in commercial software. Artificial intelligence (AI) boils down to making computers do tasks that humans could use their assistance with better.

AI models explained simply

Our senses and life experiences form the basis of our mental conceptions of the world. The more we understand, the more complicated these models become. On the other hand, computer science can streamline some model-based decision-making. We are familiar with this from our work with basic programming rules and models. On the other hand, artificial intelligence is all about programs that learn from their mistakes—or, more specifically, our data. It is probable that the algorithms developed by data scientists will only capture a subset of the complexity of the models we intend to build.

We may not be able to store as much data in our brains as the models we employ in business operations, but they are capable of processing enormous volumes of data. With the use of algorithms for things like grouping and projection, they can examine and link this data efficiently. Because of this, we may deduce meaning from varied data sets about things like customer status or corporate processes.

In a short amount of time, the models analyze this data and give us useful insights, which we can use to spot issues or choose the best course of action. Like a brain, they take in information from the past and apply it to a model that isn't very basic but is still simpler than human cognition.

The different levels of AI

Terry: As a result of its ability to rapidly digest massive amounts of data, AI can manage simplified challenges. But AI doesn't always have to be there. What are the various stages of AI and when do you think it would be useful to employ it?

Jürgen: Decision support allows for a range of cognitive levels to be accommodated. What makes a person intelligent is not always easy to pin down. Perceived intelligence is the same as actual intelligence, in my opinion. A key performance indicator (KPI) or report that gives a timely number relevant for customer contact or sales decision-making could be an example of anything intelligent. The fact that it is ideal for that moment in time renders it static and devoid of any signs or changes.

The limitations of human vision mean that static figures and graphs can only show you two dimensions, yet they can still assist you make decisions by showing you trends. However, artificial intelligence (AI) surpasses human capacity to evaluate massive data sets and draw conclusions. On the other hand, costs like programming and data collecting will be incurred.

Use cases where AI adds the most value

Terry: The cost of handling massive amounts of data is something you brought up. Can you tell me where you think AI will be most useful?

Jürgen: In situations when it can shorten time to completion, AI really shines. Having said that, it's not necessarily economical. In the end, it all comes down to the data, the lifeblood of every algorithm. Algorithm training relies heavily on the data's kind, accuracy, and heterogeneity.

Regardless, you need still calculate the expenses of processing the data and decide whether AI is worth the investment for a particular business process or decision. Terry: The field of generative AI has grown exponentially in the past several years; let's explore it more. To what extent does Gen AI stand out and pique your interest?

Jürgen: The rapid rise of generative AI's profile was the most striking development for me. Things like asking a question and instantly receiving a summary from a mountain of data are concrete examples. The potential benefits of this are obvious. When opposed to, instance, a backend algorithm that proposes recommendations based on specific data, discussing its usefulness is far easier. Though practical, those are less concrete. The usefulness of Gen AI is readily apparent to all.

With applications like sentiment analysis, language conversions, and automatic summaries, AI is constantly present in our lives. But, from an individual standpoint, it is not possible to foresee all commercial tasks. It's not enough to just process data and get a result; what's interesting is also the creation of fresh knowledge. Intriguing as it may be, the creative process can also be rather intimidating. There is no cause for concern as long as it remains within the appropriate parameters inside our program.

Approach to generative AI at SAP ensure reliable results and training models

Jürgen: Dependability is really paramount. The data input has a significant impact on the quality of the findings. Some algorithms, such as account matching, may not work well with highly diverse datasets. Outliers may be unnoticed as a result. Consequently, knowing the desired data format, required data quantity, and quality signal locations is crucial. Pick the data that will serve your company, or at least a portion of it, best. This is the most accurate representation of how often specific analysis occur within the system.

Justifying the direction of the findings is of the utmost importance. Keep in mind that it's a process, so things may not be exactly as intended. Your faith and confidence in the system will grow as you utilize it more frequently. It's something that we're all becoming used to. Verifying anything in a controlled environment is easy. Its credibility could be called into doubt if the outcomes fall short of expectations. But think of a casual user who tries to answer a complicated question every so often. They may settle for a faulty response due to their inability to evaluate its accuracy. Consequently, we require systems that provide clients with explanations of the results, fostering their confidence and comprehension of data handling.

Terry: Definitely; you must have faith in the model's predictions if you intend to act upon them. The source of the data doesn't matter if it's human or artificial. Coming up next, the responsibility-related third portion of the question. Assuring accountability with our AI and fostering trust with our partners and customers is, in my opinion, a significant differentiation for SAP.

Jürgen: Assuring data security is a responsibility that we hold dear. Many huge language models are located in an external cloud, and we are reluctant to share our intellectual property with them. To make sure our data can be used in these models without revealing its source, we need to transform, encrypt, and clean it properly. We're dedicated to completing this massive work. Occasionally, for the sake of our own environment's security, we must implement some of these models. The use cases we present are also morally solid because we take responsibility seriously.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

An intelligent user assistance system would be considered a closed-domain quality assurance challenge in this study. This research aims to fill that gap by detailing a quality assurance system applicable to the "SAP ERP user help" domain that makes use of text categorization machine

learning techniques. The following are the main parts of the intelligent user support system that has been proposed:

1. A user request corpus can be created, cleaned up, and expanded through the process of content acquisition.
2. An analysis of the request, which involves classifying it thoroughly and determining which SAP module it pertains to.
3. The process of building a database of information with the aim of categorizing questions and their potential answers.
4. Formulating a list of probable causes for the particular type of problem that is being encountered.
5. Gathering data from SAP to investigate potential sources of the problem.
6. Think about what's in the SAP "tables, the system log, and the user information" when you answer the merging question.
7. The response has been pre-approved by an authority in the field. It will be sent to the user if the response is right.

R will add the request and the appropriate class to its training set if the response is erroneous. A previously taught algorithm that has been enhanced through time.

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Figure 2. Architecture of SAP ERP data intelligence

Request Classification Algorithm

A wide variety of machine learning techniques can be employed to accomplish the common task of text classification. Request classification, which offers multi-class classification, is one example of such a task. There were efforts to build more complex algorithms, like recurrent convolutional neural networks, to do this job, but the accuracy improvement was not noticeable. The initial data came from the SAP ERP support database and was supplied by one of India's most prosperous companies. Every request is initially categorized into six main groups, or modules, in accordance with the business processes implemented in the SAP ERP system and it was shown in figure 2. Professionals have categorized the requests from each module into one of the classes (C) on the list. The main groups, sometimes called modules, are as follows:

- Making purchases and signing contracts.
- Management of property and resources.
- The budget's preparation and execution.
- Building and overseeing the operation of residential and commercial properties.
- Payments, business travel, and catering expenses.
- The control and authorization of users.

Naive Bayes Algorithm (NB)

Although it is one of the most easy techniques to multi-class analysis, Naive Bayes is also one of the most successful methods. It is based on the Bayesian Rule, which is a statistical methodology. There is a possibility that the following equation (1) can be utilized in order to determine the probability that document d belongs to class c given that equation:

$$p(c|d) = \frac{p(d|c).p(c)}{p(d)} \quad (1)$$

K Nearest Neighbors (KNN)

One of the classes that will be produced by the K Nearest Neighbors approach is the one that contains the training requests that are the most comparable to the one that is currently being classified. In order to select this class, a comparison will be made between the training requests and the one that is now being classed. The application of a wide variety of similarity measures is what has accelerated the development of various different subtypes of kNN methods. (2) The Euclidean standard is utilized in order to ascertain the distance between the two points.

$$p(u, x_i) = \left(\sum_{j=1}^n |u^j - x_i^j|^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Support Vector Machine (SVM)

The non-probabilistic classification method that is now popularly referred to as the Support Vector Machine was initially presented by V. Vapnik, who was the first person to do so. Within the context of this method, the technique of empirical risk minimization is utilized in order to generate a hyperplane within a feature space that possesses a high dimension. The Support

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Vector Machine (SVM) is a technique that can be utilized to categorize data into either of two distinct groups. Combining multiple binary "one-against-all" or "one-against-one" SVM classifiers is generally considered to be the standard way for doing multiclass classification using support vector machines (SVM). The classification method known as "one-against-one" is yet another application that can be utilized for this strategy. The number of "one-against-all" optimization jobs that we have is determined by the total number of classes that we will be optimizing. The duties that are listed below are exactly the same as these:

$$\min_{w, b, \xi} \frac{1}{2} w^T w + c \sum_{i=1}^l \xi_i$$

Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt)

An example of a probabilistic log-linear classifier is logistic multinomial regression, which aims to maximize the log-likelihood of a set of weighted features that are generated from input data. There is another term for this method, which is maximal entropy. It is also known by this name. It is possible to determine which category, c , the request x belongs to after doing the calculation of the greatest likelihood, which is denoted by the expression $p(c|x)$.

$$p(c|x) = \frac{\exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^N w_i f_i(c, x)\right)}{\sum_{c' \in C} \exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^N w_i f_i(c', x)\right)} \quad (3)$$

CONCLUSIONS

In the field of artificial intelligence, one of the most challenging problems is referred to as "question answering," and it refers to the ability to comprehend questions that are posed by people and provide solutions that are suitable. One of the subfields within the field of computer science is known as quality assurance (QA), and its primary areas of concentration include natural language processing and information retrieval. when compared to the quality assurance systems that are available to the general public. A SAP ERP user assistance solution that is powered by automated means is presented in the following paragraphs. The major processes that are involved in developing the corpus, recognizing the problem, and deriving a solution are described in detail in this document, which lays out a clear architecture to offer the means for the system to progress. The system requires the collaborative efforts of human experts for data preparation, building a knowledge database, text mining techniques, and machine learning algorithms of multi-class classification with the goal of achieving a high level of accuracy in understanding and responding to natural language requests. Additionally, the system is scalable on a variety of problems involving closed-domain question answering in a variety of domains. The system, on the other hand, is scalable across a large variety of closed-domain question-answering difficulties that are applicable to numerous domains.

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Citation: Vedaprada Raghunath. User support solution implementation for SAP ERP utilizing Artificial Intelligence to drive automated. International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research and Development (IJAIRD), 2(1), 2024, pp. 123-134.

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